

USE OF HISTORICAL MATERIALS IN PRIMARY GRADES

Associate Professor, Department of Primary Education,

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

Bovanova Umida Abdurahobovna

e-mail: umidabovanova8@gmail.com

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

Faculty of Pedagogy, Major in Primary Education

Student

Diyora Sherzodovna Irisqulova

e-mail:irisqulovadiyora@gmail.com

Abstract. Using mathematics as an example, this article presents the essence, theoretical foundations, and analysis of concepts aimed at developing historical thinking. It examines the stages of development of students' historical thinking in the educational process, as well as the integrative significance of understanding historical consciousness and national identity.

Keywords: historical thinking, historical consciousness, historical memory, independent thinking, values, creative thinking, scientists, Khorezm, Beruni, teacher, student, historical thinking.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tarixiy tafakkurni shakllantirishga qaratilgan tushunchalarning mazmunmohiyati, nazariy asoslar, tahlillari matematika fani misolida keltirib o`tilgan. Ta`lim-tarbiya jarayonida o`quvchilarning tarixiy tafakkurini shakllantirishning rivojlantirish bosqichlar hamda tarixiy ong va milliy o`zlikni anlashning integratsion ahamiyati haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tarixiy tafakkur, tarixiy ong, tarixiy xotira, mustaqil fikrlash, qadriyatlar, kreativ fikrlash, allomalar, Xorazmiy, Beruniy, o`qituvchi, o`quvchi,

tarixiy fikr.

Аннотация. В данной статье на примере математики представлены сущность, теоретические основы и анализ концепций, направленных на формирование исторического мышления. Рассматриваются этапы развития исторического мышления учащихся в образовательном процессе, а также интегративное значение понимания исторического сознания и национальной идентичности.

Ключевые слова: историческое мышление, историческое сознание, историческая память, самостоятельное мышление, ценности, творческое мышление, ученые, Хорезм, Беруни, учитель, ученик, историческое мышление.

Introduction. The Decree No. 2834 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, dated March 15, 2017, states the following: "In the 8th–9th centuries, the great scholar Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, who lived and worked in the East, wrote numerous treatises on mathematics, geometry, astronomy, history, geography, and other sciences. He was among the first to establish and apply the number “zero,” the decimal system, and polar coordinates. Muhammad al-Khwarizmi laid the foundation for the science of algebra and the theory of algorithmization, and developed precise rules for presenting scientific information and treatises."

In the educational process, fostering independent thinking in students has always been a pressing issue. Ancient and medieval Eastern and European thinkers strongly emphasized that a child must form their own opinion during the educational process. Aristotle, Socrates, Musa al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Biruni, Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Navoi and many other scholars regarded the ability to think independently as a fundamental characteristic of personal development. Based on an analysis of research conducted on this issue, the formation of independent thinking is a multifaceted process, It is

necessary to emphasize that, based on the analysis of research on this issue, the formation of independent thinking is a multifaceted process, and representatives of various sciences have approached the problem from their own research perspectives, focusing on its solution.

In the many centuries of mathematics' development from its earliest periods to the present day, four stages of development are identified.

The period of the emergence of mathematics, characterized by the accumulation (collection) of initial elements. During this period, mathematics was not yet a separate science with its own subject matter and methods; instead, only individual mathematical facts were collected. The mathematical concept of quantity was taken from human experience and was not incorporated into the framework of an independently abstracted method of investigation. In general, the mathematics of this period was practical in nature and lacked a scientific theory. Examples of this include the mathematics of ancient Egypt, Babylon, China, and India.

The period of elementary mathematics. This era was laid the foundation by ancient Greek mathematicians and was continued by scholars of the Middle East in Central Asia. It covers the period from the 6th–5th centuries BC to the 17th century AD. During this period, mathematics emerged as a distinct discipline with its own subject matter and methods. For example, in the 6th–5th centuries BC, ancient Greek mathematics developed an abstract and rigorously reasoned geometry. This became known as Euclidean geometry. In addition, branches of mathematics such as arithmetic of whole and rational numbers, the foundations of a general theory of ratios similar to Dedekind's cut theory, elements of the theory of limits, and the “Exhaustive Method” for calculating area and volume emerge.

In the countries of Central Asia, Muhammad al-Khwarizmi elevated algebra to the status of a distinct science by creating it. The scholars of the “Central Asia” encyclopedia—Al-Farghāni, Abu Rayhān al-Bīrūnī, Abu Ali Ibn Sīnā, Umar Khayyām, Ulugh Beg, Ghiyāth al-Dīn al-Kāshī, and others—contributed to the

science of mathematics.

The Khurasani mathematician Nasir al-Din al-Tusi systematized plane and spherical trigonometry in the 13th century and elevated trigonometry to the status of a separate discipline.

The era of algebra of variable quantities.

This covers the period from the 17th century to the second half of the 19th century. The significance of the beginning of this period is that the great French scientist René Descartes introduced variables into mathematics, and in the works of I. Newton and G. W. Leibniz, differential and integral calculus was created.

Mathematics of this period is also called “Classical Higher Mathematics.”

In the 19th and 20th centuries, the scope of spatial forms and quantitative relationships that can be examined by mathematical methods expands enormously. A great many mathematical theories emerge, and the range of applications of mathematics greatly increases. New branches of mathematics emerge. Since the mathematical materials taught in elementary school correspond to the ideas and discoveries that arose in the second period of mathematical development, in our research we focus on O In our research, we focus on the work of historians of mathematics who have highlighted the works of medieval Eastern scholars.

In her work titled “The Doctrine of Number in the Medieval East,” G. P. Matvievsckaya, a corresponding member of the Russian Academy of Sciences, discusses Al-Khwarizmi, Al-Farghāni, Al-Fārābi, at-Tūsī, Al-Kāshī, Qāzīzāda Rūmī, A brief biography and activity of Ali Qushchi and others are provided. The book also provides a general overview of the history of mathematics in Central Asia. This book is interesting in that it also presents very interesting information about the lives of medieval scholars. The third book, co-authored by G. L. Matvievsckaya and X. Tillashev, is the result of work based on manuscripts of mathematicians and astronomers from the 10th to the 18th centuries. The book provides materials on the history of science in Central Asia. The book includes a

brief description of the manuscripts, supplemented by the author's bibliographic information and their locations. The degree of study of the work is indicated, and its title and a brief description are provided. The book is also interesting in that the accounts of the authors' lives are presented in chronological order.

This scholarly work provides information on manuscripts by authors not currently known to science, as well as on unknown works. This book can also be used as an index for the history of mathematics in Central Asia.

Our scientific research is directly related to G. M. Glazer's book, "Mathematics History in the School" (4th–7th centuries) (1981). This book is written in very simple language and is an important methodological guide on the development of the history of mathematics.

This book is designed to increase students' interest in learning mathematics, broaden their intellectual horizons, and enrich their culture. It is dedicated to the history of the origins of arithmetic, the beginnings of algebra, and the development of geometry. Some of the proofs in the book can be used in the early grades.

– Methods for using historical materials in learning number representation.

At this stage, the teacher's task is to develop counting skills in children, reveal the structure of the natural number sequence in the range 1–10, and on that basis define a number as an element of a natural sequence.

To this end, it is necessary to ensure that students achieve the following:

- a) They must master the sequence of numbers from 1 to 10;
- b) they must be able to count objects and, when the counting order is given, state each object's sequential number within a given group;
- c) they must consciously internalize how each number in the sequence from 1 to 10 is formed (by adding 1 to the previous number or by subtracting 1 from the number that follows);
- d) be able to read numbers and match each (printed or written) number with the corresponding number of objects;

j) They must know how to compare numbers (the corresponding exercises are performed without using $>$, $<$, or $=$ symbols);

k) They must have a solid grasp of all cases of the numerical composition of the numbers 2, 3, 4, and 5 as two addends;

l) They must be able to read mathematical notations such as $4+1$, $3-1$, $2+1$, etc., and know how to match these notations with corresponding pictures. They must be able to solve the corresponding problems with full certainty and write their solutions using numeral cards ($2+2=4$, $4-1=3$, $3+2=5$, etc.);

m) They must be able to distinguish a circle, a square, and a triangle from one another and name each.

We will provide a detailed description of the methodology for working on each of these areas. A student who has mastered the sequence of numbers well can recite it correctly and in reverse order starting from any number, and can state the number that comes after a given number in counting, the number that comes between two numbers, and the number that comes before a given number. In addition to the exercises in the textbook, the following exercises also help develop these skills:

- Look at this number (the teacher shows, for example, the number 5) and take that many cubes.

- How many dolls are on the shelf? Show that many. (The children show the corresponding number card.)

- Which card is turned upside down? (Which number “escaped”? Which number “hid”?). (The children show the corresponding number card and numeral card.)

- Show the number's neighbor to the left. Show the number's neighbor to the right. Show the number's neighbors. (The children show the corresponding cards.)

Summarizing the information above, historical consciousness emerges as an element, a component, of social consciousness in its various forms, and its evolution and diversity are determined by the evolution and diversity of nature and

society. An element of this philosophical worldview is the philosophy of history, or historical consciousness, which brings to life the past state of society's development. In works dedicated to the genesis of historical consciousness, many researchers are confined to European traditions. Proponents of Eurocentrism believe that the formation of historical consciousness first appeared in Greece in the 5th century BC in Herodotus's famous *Histories*.

From an empirical point of view, Herodotus's work is considered the first true historical work. Although it is known that the first sprouts of historical consciousness appeared in the East—the cradle of humanity's civilization—the distinct emergence of historical consciousness is associated with Herodotus's history, and he is glorified as the father of history.

CONCLUSION

The process of the formation of historical consciousness is extremely complex and depends on many interacting factors. In particular, the formation of historical consciousness in a child is determined by the multicultural composition of the nation, as each society has its own values, traditions, religious ceremonies, and culture, which are shaped by personal experience and learning. The factors that determine historical consciousness are numerous and varied.

The historical consciousness of elementary school students is formed under the influence of various factors. At the same time, its state is primarily influenced by the knowledge acquired in the course of teaching subjects and in extracurricular activities, their objectivity and reliability depend on both the content of school textbooks and the teachers' positions, since schoolchildren hardly use historical materials in their learning processes.

For them, historical information only needs to be reflected in the content of history and social sciences.

Today, it is appropriate to incorporate into existing primary school textbooks content aimed at fostering a child's historical consciousness. Humanity's historical

consciousness has its own genesis and has come a long way. Its formation has proceeded hand in hand with humanity's economic and political development. Although historical consciousness and historical memory form an integral unity, historical consciousness is primary. When historical consciousness is formed and has reached its full development, historical memory is manifested at a high level in an individual, a people, or a nation. Historical consciousness is the realization that everything, even spiritual existence, has happened—a concept present in all knowledge. The effective use of historical materials, their inherent unity, and the establishment of interdisciplinary connections in teaching subjects in the early grades make a significant contribution to the process of self-awareness.

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